

Project: NAMS. Latvian Identity and Knowledge Strategies as Resources for Societal Resilience

Version 1

Description

NAMS project focuses on the question of how Latvian identity functions as a resource for societal resilience in conditions of geopolitical uncertainty. The project particularly highlights the folklife sphere as a resource for ethnic identity, and the issues of knowledge production and interpretation. The identity resources, risks, and visions for the future are explored based on: interviews (4 datasets), a national survey (2 datasets), a key folk narrative corpus, an archival corpus of reflexive ethnography, and a database of folklore collection campaigns.

The project "NAMS. Latvian Identity and Knowledge Strategies as Resources for Societal Resilience" is implemented in the framework of the State Research Programme "LETONIKA for the Development of a Latvian and European Society" (No. VPP-IZM-LETONIKA-2025/1-0008).

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

NAMS. Latvian Identity and

Knowledge Strategies as Resources for Societal Resilience (2025-2028)

Researchers

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Organizations

Institute of Literature, Folklore and Art of the University of Latvia,
Latvian Academy of Culture, University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Project: NAMS. Latvian Identity and Knowledge Strategies as Resources for Societal Resilience

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grants: NAMS. Latvian Identity and Knowledge Strategies as Resources for Societal Resilience (2025-2028)

Project:

3. License

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Access Rights: Public

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4. Templates

Descriptions

Sources of reflexive ethnography in the Archives of Latvian Folklore

Collection of the field diaries of Latvian folklorists from the early Soviet period, documenting the process of folklore collecting in Jēkabpils and Ventspils region (1952) and Cēsis and Alūksne region (1953). The collection consists of 19 hand-written notebooks, digitized in 569 scanned and transcribed files on the platform garamantas.lv.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The activity aims to create a source revealing a specific period in the history of Latvian folkloristics, an attempt at a reflexive ethnography of the 1950s. The collection will provide insight into various contexts that inform the field production of archived folklore: cultural-political assignments imposed on folklore researchers by thdre regime, interaction and communication between folklorists and informants, fieldworkers' personalities and preferences, etc. Additionally, the collection will expose perceptive portrayals of everyday and cultural life in the Latvian countryside in the 1950s as observed by folklore researchers.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Machine-readable text
- Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- HTML
- JPG

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

500

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

Yes

1.1.7 If Yes, please indicate what data set are you re-using?

Archives of Latvian Folklore

<https://humma.lv/en>

id: null, Type: url

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Folklore research, academic work in the Soviet era, reflexive approaches

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

Historical metadata standard of the Archives of Latvian Folklore

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Humma.lv

<https://humma.lv/en>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Internet browser

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2027-12-31

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

2.4.6 Other relevant remarks

Data are selected and prepared by experts in the field of folklore studies and archiving.

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

Funded by the project "NAMS. Latvian Identity and Knowledge Strategies as Resources for Societal Resilience", State Research Programme "LETONIKA for the Development of a Latvian and European Society", No. VPP-IZM-LETONIKA-2025/1-0008.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

- Ieva Weaver (0000-0003-3363-3552)
- Ilga Vālodze Ābele (0000-0002-4251-6350)
- Sandis Laime (0000-0002-6529-6303)
- Dace Bula (0000-0002-5418-4648)

Dace Bula - content selection

Sandis Laime - infrastructure and metadata consulting

Ilga Vālodze Ābelkina - preparation of the dataset

Ieva Weaver - project managing, planning

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

Maintenance will be funded from the budget of the Institute of Literature, Folklore and Art of the University of Latvia

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

The field diaries were created in the first half of the 1950s. The authors are deceased. Diaries contain personal and ideological data of historical value. The authors were aware of their archiving and potential public use.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

Privacy policies

The data contain historical data, sometimes of sensitive character, which have been archived by consent. Data sharing follows the privacy policy of the Institute of Literature, Folklore and Art of the University of Latvia.

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